

CONVERSION OF LDPE INTO TRANSPORTATION FUELS BY A TWO-STAGE PROCESS USING Ni/Al-SBA-15 AS CATALYST

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Abstract

Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts with Si/Al atomic ratios within the 20 – 135 range were prepared by a post synthesis grafting procedure, having nickel contents between 6 and 11%. The addition of Ni to the Al-SBA-15 support caused a decrease of the BET surface area and pore volume. Additionally, larger Ni particles were attained over the catalysts with higher Si/Al atomic ratios, indicating the existence of some interaction between aluminium species and nickel particles. Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts displayed remarkable properties for the preparation of diesel fuels in the hydroreforming of the oils obtained from the LDPE thermal cracking. On increasing the Si/Al atomic ratios of the Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts, higher share of light and heavy diesel were attained, the sum reaching a maximum (67.3%) for Ni/Al-SBA-15(70). This was caused by the higher extent of oligomerization reactions on enhancing the Si/Al atomic ratio. Additionally, around 85 – 90% of the starting olefins were successfully hydrogenated and the aromatic content was rather low (below 5%), without almost any polyaromatic compound (< 0.1 %).

Keywords: hydroreforming; LDPE; Ni/Al-SBA-15; fuels

1. Introduction

Plastic wastes are a subject of deep environmental concern in developed societies. The total amount of plastic wastes generated in 2011 only in Europe was around 25.1 million tonnes [1]. The main components of this plastic waste stream were polyolefins (LDPE, HDPE and PP) in a share close to 60%. Several strategies can be used to deal with these wastes according to the following waste management hierarchy [2]: reduce, reuse, recycle, recovery and landfilling. Currently, around 42% of the plastics wastes in Europe end up in landfills while 33% are recovered to obtain energy and the remaining 24% are recycled mechanically. The share of landfilling is required to drop due to the progressively more stringent EU legislation. In this regard, the current preferred choices to deal with these plastics wastes (mechanical recycling and direct energy recovery) have some evident limitations for increasing their respective shares. Thus, for mechanical recycling, there is a progressive loss in quality after successive heating-molding cycles so it can only be regarded as an intermediate treatment. On the other hand, direct energy recovery is not accepted by the public opinion of many countries (e.g. Spain) because of the odours and the emission of toxic compounds (dioxins, furans). Therefore, the development of new processes to deal with plastics wastes is a highly desirable option.

Polyolefins can be converted into hydrocarbon mixtures by means of thermal and catalytic pyrolysis [3-7]. However, the usage of a catalyst shows the added advantages of reducing the cracking temperature as well as tailoring the selectivity. One aspect to be considered in the catalytic cracking of plastics is the presence of accessible acid sites since polyolefins are bulky molecules which show steric hindrances to enter the zeolite micropores. In this regard, ordered mesoporous materials such as Al-MCM-41[3] and hierarchical zeolites have shown enhanced activities in the catalytic cracking of polyolefins [8]. Initially, the obtained

hydrocarbon mixtures are promising for the preparation of fuels since they are mostly made up by components within the gasoline and diesel ranges. However, these hydrocarbons mixtures cannot be directly used as fuels since they contained a great deal of olefins, exceeding the currently existing limits on EU laws (18 wt % for gasolines).

In previous works, we have reported a two stage process for the preparation of hydrocarbon mixtures with improved properties to be used in the formulation of fuels [9-11]. This process comprises firstly of a thermal cracking of LDPE followed by a subsequent catalytic hydroreforming of the oil previously obtained in the thermal cracking. The tested catalysts were bifunctional ones based on nickel supported over hierarchical Beta and ZSM-5 zeolites as well as Al-MCM-41 and Al-SBA-15 carriers. The results obtained over Ni/Al-SBA-15 were especially remarkable since this catalyst allowed obtaining the highest share of light diesel (32.3 %, C₁₃ – C₁₈) and heavy diesel fractions (19.9%, C₁₉ – C₄₀). This diesel also displayed very high correlated cetane indexes (CCI) (> 70), due to its highly paraffinic content. Additionally, Ni/Al-SBA-15 succeeded in the hydrogenation of more than 95% of the starting olefins of the fuels, and also, it yielded little aromatics (< 5 wt %). In the present work, we have explored the possibility of enhancing the diesel share and its properties in the hydroreforming of the oils from LDPE thermal cracking by modifying the Si/Al atomic ratio of the Al-SBA-15 support. In this regard, pure silica SBA-15 was grafted with aluminium by a post synthesis procedure, due to the difficulty for incorporating aluminium by a direct synthesis route, obtaining Al-SBA-15 with Si/Al atomic ratios within the 20 – 135 range. Afterwards the supports were impregnated with Ni and activated, being tested in the hydroreforming of the oil from LDPE thermal cracking.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis of the support Al-SBA-15

Pure silica SBA-15 was previously synthesized according to the procedure of Zhao et al. [12]. Subsequently, Al was grafted by means of a post synthesis procedure reported by Zeng et al. [13], being next described. Initially, solution A, formed by 100 mL of distilled water plus hydrated aluminium trichloride ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ purum p.a., crystallized, $\geq 99.0\%$ Sigma-Aldrich), was stirred at 60 °C for 30 min. Subsequently, solution B, containing 100 mL of distilled water plus tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAOH 10 wt% in water, Sigma-Aldrich) with a molar ratio TMAOH / Al of 2 was added over A, holding the initial conditions for 1 h. Then, 2 g of pure silica SBA-15 was added keeping constant the same temperature and under stirring for 5 h. The solid products so obtained were separated by filtration, washed several times with distilled water, dried overnight at 110 °C and calcined in air at 550 °C for 5 h. The obtained samples were named as Al-SBA-15(x), wherein x stands for the Si/Al atomic ratio loaded in the post synthesis treatment.

2.2. Impregnation of the supports

Al-SBA-15 was impregnated by the incipient wetness technique with a nickel chloride solution using a (solution volume) / (pore volume) ratio of 1. The amount of Ni added was 10 wt % referred to the mass of catalyst. Prior to the impregnation, the solid support was outgassed in a rotavapor under vacuum. Then, 1,5 g of sample was impregnated and subjected again to rotation and vacuum. The dry material was calcined under static air at 550 °C for 5 h. Subsequently, the catalyst was activated by hydrogen reduction (30 ml/min) in a fixed bed reactor with a heating rate of 2 °C/min up to 550°C and holding this temperature for 30 min.

2.3. Catalysts characterization

The crystallinity of the catalysts was checked by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) in a Phillips X'PERT MPD diffractometer using Cu-K α radiation. XRD patterns within the 10 – 70° range were recorded using a step size and a counting time of 0.1° and 10 s, respectively. The identification of the different crystalline phases present was performed by comparison with the corresponding JCPDS cards. The silicon, aluminium and nickel contents of the catalysts were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES) on a VARIAN Vista AX Axial CCD Simultaneous ICP-AES apparatus. Previously, the samples were digested by acid treatment with H₂SO₄ and HF.

Nitrogen adsorption – desorption isotherms at 77 K were obtained in a Micromeritics Tristar 3000 device. The analyses were carried out after outgassing the samples at 350 °C under vacuum for 16 h. BET surface areas analyses were determined by applying the BET equation to the relative pressure range of 0.05 – 0.16 in the nitrogen adsorption isotherm as range of linearity.

Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) were collected on a Phillips TECNAI 20 microscope equipped with a LaB₆ filament under an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Prior to the observation, the samples were dispersed in acetone, stirred in an ultrasonic bath and finally deposited over a carbon – coated copper grid.

2.4. LDPE thermal cracking

The thermal cracking reactions of the virgin LDPE were carried out in a stirred 100 mL stainless-steel autoclave reactor provided with gases inlet and outlet and heated by a ceramic oven. In the experiment, 30 g of the pure polyolefin (LDPE) was thermally cracked at 400°C for 90 minutes under 1.5 bar of nitrogen. The obtained thermal cracking product consisted of a hydrocarbon mixture within the C₂ – C₄₀ range.

2.5 . *Hydroreforming reactions*

The figure 2 shows the scheme of the experimental procedure. The hydroreforming reactions were carried out in the same stirred stainless-steel autoclave reactor previously used in the polyolefin thermal cracking. The feed of the hydroreforming reactor consists of the oils resulting from the LDPE thermal cracking (C₄ – C₄₀ hydrocarbon mixture). In each experiment, 20 g of the thermal cracking product and the hydroreforming catalyst were added to the autoclave reactor and hydrogen was loaded (cold charge). Then, the reactor was closed and the catalytic reaction was carried out at the selected temperature for a fixed time under stirring (N=700 rpm). After finishing the reaction, the reactor was left cooling to room temperature. Subsequently, the volatile products were separated into gaseous and liquid fractions in an ice cooled condenser, the former being collected in a gas bag. Finally, the liquid product from the reactor was filtered to separate the solid catalyst.

2.5. *Analyses of the hydroreforming products*

The hydroreforming liquid products were separated by distillation into hydrocarbon mixtures within the gasoline (C₅ – C₁₂) and diesel (C₁₃ – C₄₀) fractions. No heavier products than C₄₀ were detected. The analyses of both gasoline and gaseous fractions were carried out by gas

chromatography in a Varian 3800 GC using a 100 m length x 0.25 mm i.d. Chrompack capillary column. The gasoline fraction (C₅ – C₁₂) was also analyzed by the PIONA method in order to determine the respective contents of paraffins, isoparaffins, olefins, naphthenes and aromatics. The diesel fraction was analysed in a Varian 3900 GC equipped with a 25 m length methyl silicone capillary column, in order to determine the yields of light (C₁₃ – C₁₈) and heavy diesel (C₁₉ – C₄₀) fractions. The selectivities of the total hydroreforming products were lumped in four fractions: gases (C₁ – C₄), gasoline (C₅ – C₁₂), light diesel (C₁₃ – C₁₈) and heavy diesel (C₁₉ – C₄₀).

HPLC analyses of the total diesel fraction (C₁₃ – C₄₀) were carried out in a HP 1100 liquid chromatograph with a ZorbaxNH₂ packed column 25 cm length and 4.6 mm x 5 µm internal diameter to calculate the aromatic content. The olefin content was determined by calculating the bromine index according to ASTM D2710 standard with a Methrom 836 apparatus after diluting the samples in an appropriate solvent. The correlated cetane index (CCI) of the diesel was determined by the ASTM D976 rule. RON values were calculated using the Varian Detailed Hydrocarbon Analysis 5.0 software, which implements the method depicted by Durand et al. [14].

The acronyms related with fuel technology used in this work are the following ones:

LDPE: low density polyethylene

RON: research octane number

PIONA: GC analysis of the content of paraffins, isoparaffins, olefins, naphthenes and aromatics in the gasoline fraction

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst characterization

Low angle XRD patterns of the Al-SBA-15 supports (data not shown) indicates a loss of the mesoscopic ordering for both low (Al-SBA-15(15)) and high Si/Al atomic ratios (Al-SBA-15(70) and Al-SBA-15(100)). In contrast, the mesoscopic ordering is preserved in the Al-SBA-15 samples with intermediate Si/Al atomic ratios (Al-SBA-15(30) and Al-SBA-15(50)). Table 1 summarizes the main physicochemical properties of the obtained materials. The grafting procedure allowed incorporating aluminium over the SBA-15 supports although the finally loaded amounts were lower than those initially present in the synthesis medium. Thus, according to ICP analyses, the Si/Al atomic ratios of the Al-SBA-15 supports varied within 20.9 – 135.4 while the range corresponding to the theoretical content was 15 – 100. On the other hand, after the Ni impregnation treatment, no variation was found in the Si/Al atomic ratio for any sample. All the catalysts contained Ni in an amount close to the theoretical one (around 9.8 – 10.9 %), except for the Ni/Al-SBA-15(30) sample, wherein a lower amount was loaded (6.1%). The addition of nickel resulted in a decrease of the BET surface area and pore volumes, due to both the dense nature of nickel and pore blockage. However, pore sizes did not show any clear trend and varied within the range 8.0 – 11.0 nm for every sample. Figure 1.a) illustrates the TEM micrographs of three chosen samples (Ni/Al-SBA-15(15), Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) and Ni/Al-SBA-15(100)) while Figure 1.b) depicts the nickel particles size distribution, obtained by direct counting of more than 100 particles from the TEM images. Figure 1.a) clearly shows that smaller and more dispersed nickel particles were observed for Ni/Al-SBA-15(15) while larger and more aggregated particles were appreciated for Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) and especially, for Ni/Al-SBA-15(100). Seemingly, the nickel particle size was increased for higher Si/Al atomic ratios, since the smaller particles were detected for Ni/Al-SBA-15(15) with roughly 81% of the nickel particles with a size within the range 10 – 30 nm (see Figure 1.b)). In contrast, both Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) and Ni/Al-SBA-15(100) exhibited much larger

particles sizes, with around 50% of their nickel particles larger than 30 nm. This fact indicates that the occurrence of higher aluminium contents in the Al-SBA-15 support originates an enhanced interaction with the nickel particles which prevents its further aggregation into bigger crystals.

3.2. Catalytic hydroreforming of the oils from LDPE thermal cracking over Ni/Al-SBA-15

The oil obtained from the thermal cracking of LDPE is a hydrocarbon mixture with a broad distribution within the $C_4 - C_{40}$ range. **Figure 3** displays the oil selectivity by groups, wherein it can be appreciated that its main components were gasoline (45.5%, $C_5 - C_{12}$), light diesel (34.4 %, $C_{13} - C_{18}$) and heavy diesel (15.3%, $C_{19} - C_{40}$), while the share of gases was rather low (4.2 %, $C_1 - C_4$). **Figure 4** exhibits the corresponding selectivity by atom carbon number which shows the typical broad hydrocarbon distribution with a main maximum placed at C_{10} (12.3%). This hydrocarbon distribution proceeds from a random radical cracking mechanism [15]. Additionally, the feed oil contains high amount of olefins since its bromine index (see Table 2) is 64.2 g Br_2 / 100 g of sample while the aromatics content is virtually negligible (below 0.1 %). This high content of olefins is undesirable since it may lead to the formation of gums in the engines. Therefore, its content must be diminished, e. g. by means of hydroreforming technologies.

The selectivity by groups obtained in the hydroreforming of the oil from LDPE thermal cracking over the different Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts is shown in **Figure 3**. A clear trend may be envisaged with the Si/Al atomic ratio of the Al-SBA-15 support. As the aluminium content decreases, the share of gasoline drops from 44.3% (Ni/Al-SBA-15(15)) to 30.2% (Ni/Al-SBA-15(100)). In parallel, the amount of light diesel is enhanced from 36.4 to 40.5% and the corresponding one of heavy diesel is also augmented from 18.7 to 24.2 %, respectively. Additionally, the share of gaseous hydrocarbons is rather low, always below 5 wt %. Accordingly,

the medium acid strength of the Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts did not result in hydrocracking towards lighter products. Instead, the decrease in the amount of acid sites (higher Si/Al atomic ratios) combined with the occurrence of larger Ni particles resulted in the oligomerization of the lighter hydrocarbons, mostly gasolines, increasing the proportion of diesel. Considering both diesels, the sum adds up to 67.3 % over Ni/Al-SBA-15(70), which constitutes the highest share of both diesels obtained in the hydroreforming of the oil from LDPE thermal cracking. In contrast, over Ni/Al-SBA-15(15), the sum of both light and heavy diesel was only raised to 55.1%. Consequently, Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) constitutes a really remarkable catalyst for obtaining diesel by means of oligomerization reactions.

Figure 4 illustrates the selectivity by carbon atom number wherein it is appreciated that the increase in the Si/Al atomic ratio caused the appearance of a broad peak within $C_{12} - C_{23}$ with a maximum placed at C_{16} (around 6 – 7%) (Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) and Ni/Al-SBA-15(100)). Interestingly, the share of hydrocarbons higher than C_{31} is virtually zero, so the formation of heavier hydrocarbons, not useful as transportation fuels, can be regarded as negligible.

Table 2 summarizes the main properties of the obtained fuels. Interestingly, the content of olefins decreases in a large extent during the hydroreforming so the bromine index drops to just 6.5 – 7.5 g Br_2 / 100 g of sample. This means that around 85 – 90% of the starting olefins have been successfully hydrogenated. Additionally, no relationship is observed between the Ni particle size of the catalysts and the hydrogenation degree of the fuels. On the other hand, the aromatic content of the fuels increased after the hydroreforming, reaching an amount within 3.7 – 5.0 wt % without showing any clear trend. It is also noteworthy that the amount of polyaromatics present in the fuels was virtually negligible in all cases (below 0.1 wt %), which especially important considering the possible application of these products as fuels. For the gasolines, a maximum in the amount of n-paraffins was found (84.2%, Ni/Al-SBA-15(50)) due to the

hydrogenation of the corresponding linear 1-olefins. Likewise, a maximum was also obtained for the isoparaffins (15.0%, Ni/Al-SBA-15(30)). Considering the whole of these data, it seems that the obtained hydrocarbon mixtures show promising properties to be used as fuels. From all the studied catalyst, Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) can be regarded as the optimum one, since it shows the highest selectivity toward diesels with negligible content of polyaromatics, being its nature mostly n-paraffinic.

The catalyst recover after reaction was exposed to the regeneration treatment consisted of carrying out firstly a calcinations under static air at 550°C for 5 h and subsequently, reducing the catalyst under a flow of hydrogen (30 ml/min) with a heating rate of 2°C/min up to 550°C and holding this temperature for 30 min. After this treatment the properties of the catalyst were analyzed by nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms at 77K (BET Surface Area = 355 m² g⁻¹, Pore Volume = 0.56 cm³ g⁻¹, Mesopore Volume= 0.53 cm³g⁻¹, Pore diameter= 10.6 nm) and significant changes wasn't observe respect the catalyst before the reaction. A Thermogravimetric analysis was used to determinate the amount of coke deposited on the catalyst and the result was 0% of coke after regeneration. In this case, the catalyst would be used in reaction again.

4. Conclusions

Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts with Si/Al atomic ratios within the 20 – 135 range were prepared by a post synthesis grafting procedure. The presence of Ni caused a decrease of both the BET surface area and the pore volumes of the catalysts. Additionally, larger Ni particles were attained over the catalysts with higher Si/Al atomic ratios. Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts displayed remarkable properties for the preparation of diesel fuels. On increasing the Si/Al atomic ratios of the Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts, higher share of light and heavy diesel were attained, the sum reaching a maximum (67.3%) for Ni/Al-SBA-15(70). This was caused by the higher extent of oligomerization

reactions and less cracking on enhancing the Si/Al atomic ratio. Additionally, around 85 – 90% of the starting olefins were successfully hydrogenated and the polyaromatic content was virtually negligible (< 0.1 %). Consequently, Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) is a remarkable catalyst for obtaining diesel by the hydroreforming process.

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4. References

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Table 1. Physicochemical properties of the Ni/Al-SBA-15 catalysts

	Si/Al ^a	Ni (%wt) ^a	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹) ^b	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹) ^b	Mesopore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹) ^b	Pore diameter (nm) ^b
Al-SBA-15(15)	20.9	-	574	0.71	0.64	8.3
Ni/Al-SBA-15(15)	20.9	10.9	411	0.57	0.49	8.3
Al-SBA-15(30)	34.0	-	624	0.82	0.67	8.2
Ni/Al-SBA-15(30)	34.0	6.1	440	0.62	0.59	10.6
Al-SBA-15(50)	59.2	-	773	0.74	0.56	8.2
Ni/Al-SBA-15(50)	59.2	10.8	548	0.72	0.60	11.6
Al-SBA-15(70)	72.4	-	646	0.83	0.75	11.3
Ni/Al-SBA-15(70)	72.4	9.5	492	0.66	0.56	8.2
Al-SBA-15(100)	135.4	-	662	0.84	0.76	11.3
Ni/Al-SBA-15(100)	135.4	9.8	527	0.68	0.55	10.6

^a Calculated by ICP analyses; ^b N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms at 77K

Table 2. Characterization data of the obtained fuels.

	Bromine index	n-paraffins	Isoparaffins	Aromatics	Polyaromatics
	(g Br₂ / 100 g)	(wt%)^a	(wt%)^a	(wt%)^b	(wt%)^b
Feed Oil	64.2	46.73	11.81	0.08	0.08
Ni/Al-SBA-15(15)	7.4	62.23	10.26	4.14	0.01
Ni/Al-SBA-15(30)	6.8	60.87	15.05	4.90	0.16
Ni/Al-SBA-15(50)	6.8	84.19	6.27	4.17	0.06
Ni/Al-SBA-15(70)	6.6	78.83	8.94	3.75	0.01
Ni/Al-SBA-15(100)	7.5	72.15	9.76	3.76	0.00

^a Determinated by PIONA analysis gasoline; ^b Determinated by HPLC in total fuels

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. a) TEM micrographs of the catalyst Ni/Al-SBA-15(15), Ni/Al-SBA-15(70) and Ni/Al-SBA-15(100), b) Ni particle size distribution.

Figure 2. Scheme of the experimental procedure.

Figure 3. Selectivities groups obtained in the catalytic hydroreforming over Ni/Al-SBA-15 (different ratio Si/Al) of the oils from the LDPE thermal cracking ($T = 310^{\circ}\text{C}$; $t = 45$ min.; catalyst / feed ratio = 1:30; hydrogen pressure = 20 bar).

Figure 4. Selectivities by atom carbon number obtained in the catalytic hydroreforming over Ni/Al-SBA-15 (different ratio Si/Al) of the oils from the LDPE thermal cracking ($T = 310^{\circ}\text{C}$; $t = 45$ min.; catalyst / feed ratio = 1:30; hydrogen pressure = 20 bar).

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

